

Context Matters: Contextual Value-Based Deliberation in Water Consumption Scenarios

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Abstract. Values and context are important in an agent’s decision-making process. Individuals may prioritise values differently, and changing context can also necessitate different considerations. In this paper, we use Schwartz’s theory of basic human values to define ethical values and introduce a preorder to model an agent’s relative preference among those values. We characterise context using this preorder, which can then be used in socio-technical systems as part of the autonomous agents’ deliberation process. We also define the transition between contexts as shifts in value order. To illustrate our approach, we implement this preorder in a domestic water-consumption scenario featuring two towns whose citizens make daily decisions regarding showering, considering visitors, drought rules, and sports activities. Our results demonstrate how our model can effectively represent value orders and integrate them into agents’ decision-making processes. This approach also allows us to characterise contexts, understand how these contexts affect agents’ behaviour, and assess the impact of shifting contexts. We observe that the value order influences the dynamics of context transitions, making some value orders more prone to shift than others.

Keywords: value-awareness · agent decision-making · value-based context.

1 Introduction

A growing interest in modelling behaviour based on values is emerging in recent research. Values can be seen as stable drivers that determine at a high level a person’s preferred actions. However, these values, such as *universalism*, are very abstract, and

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their translation into preferences between actions is not always clear. For example, universalism would imply a concern for the wider society, but this could have different interpretations for different situations and people.

Consider a case where universalism, benevolence, and hedonism are important to a person to illustrate how values can be translated and cause decision-making conflicts.

Should they be supportive of their community (*i.e.*, be benevolent) and fill their swimming pool to allow neighbourhood children to cool off during a heatwave, or should they be more concerned about the universalism-based impacts of water conservation, adhere strictly to water restrictions, and leave the pool covered to conserve water for the greater good? Additionally, they might face the dilemma of watering their garden, which provides personal pleasure by keeping it as a small haven, versus adhering to water restrictions to conserve water for the community or, if these measures allow a certain flexibility, choosing between the garden or the swimming pool.

However, this also depends on the context. Maybe the person relies on the swimming pool for physical therapy, which is crucial for their health, or perhaps their vegetable garden is a significant source of their family's nutrition. These personal needs make it harder to follow water restrictions strictly. Alternatively, in a scenario with an ongoing severe drought, the urgency of conserving water might be more pronounced, making universalism values more salient.

The particular context makes some values more salient than others. Therefore, one can say that value prioritisation in making choices changes between different contexts.

To maintain the focus on values, in this paper we assume that it is clear when the context changes, either because the environment changes (*e.g.*, a drought starts) or a new regulation comes into play (*e.g.*, a prohibition to refill swimming pools or water gardens in a drought situation). In these cases, a person goes from one context to another rather than participating in several contexts simultaneously. The latter happens, for example, when one talks with one's boss at a Christmas party. This is both a party context and a work context. We assume that the person can determine the most salient context.

These results are also intended to support identifying requirements for a formal model, which is currently underway.

We can show that if the context change is not considered, the agents will not behave realistically. We also show that by using values, we can model some context changes in a way that induces a natural change of behaviour.

To illustrate the applicability of our approach, we use a water-consumption scenario to compare two towns with distinct contexts. Our empirical results show that our model can reflect the impact of value orders and the relative difficulties in moving between different types of value orders with equal ease. Since values are not all independent, some orderings facilitate a change of value priorities better than others.

This paper presents the results of an exploratory study using an agent-based model (ABM) that incorporates values into the agents' decision-making processes. Our approach uses value orders to characterise contexts and a mechanism to represent changes in context when an agent chooses one. The primary goal is to determine whether agents that take context, with an associated value ordering, into account when making decisions lead to agent-based simulations that better reflect human behaviour, including context changes inducing a change of behaviour.

This empirical approach provides results that are also intended to support identifying requirements for a model and architecture for multi-context, value-aware agents, which is currently underway.

We can show that the agents will not behave realistically if the context change is not considered. We can also show that using values, we can model some context changes to induce a natural behaviour change.

To illustrate the applicability of our approach, we compare two towns with distinct contexts in a water-consumption scenario. Our empirical results show that our model can quickly reflect the impact of value orders and the relative difficulties in moving between different types of value orders. Since values are not all independent, some orderings facilitate a change of value priorities better than others.

2 Background

Our agents' two main elements in the simulation are values and contexts. In this section, we give a very brief introduction to both. Contexts have been defined by [17] and are used to provide the deliberation with tangible elements that are distinct in different situations. They are things like time, location, and so on. In [4], some issues about how to recognise a context and know when it changes are identified. In [8], it is shown how contexts can be used in agent-based simulation deliberations. For simplicity, in the current paper, we only use the different value priorities to distinguish contexts. For other types of agent-based approaches in the water domain, see [5], which focuses on norm-aware simulation. Although norms may promote values, these are not explicitly represented in the deliberation. Similarly, agnostic to the domain, [9] proposes using explicit value-awareness to assess which norms are being promoted/demoted. These approaches focus on the normative aspect. Our proposal focuses on values only and the effects on agents' decisions on themselves, also exploring the different value dispositions (*i.e.*, value orders) and assessing their differences. This introduces the second element of our framework, the use of values in the agent's deliberation. Values are abstract concepts that represent the assessment or evaluation of a state of the world on various criteria associated with those values.

The need to use ethical decision-making in agents has been highlighted in [1] where the use of explicit ethical values in the agent's deliberation process (or explicit ethical machines) is discussed. What is interesting about using values, at least according to Schwartz[12, 13], is that a universal set of abstract values can be attributed to people. Cervantes [3] also differentiate the use of ethical values in artificial agents, distinguishing those that possess implicit values given by the programmer, agents that have explicit values as part of the deliberation but not implicitly hard-coded in the actions but as first-order elements. They also define the concept of full ethical agents, which only applies to humans. In other words, explicit ethical agents use the concepts as part of their logic, implementing an ethical approach. Differences between people stem not from having different values but from giving different priorities to these values. This makes it possible to use values as a starting point to compare behaviours. The downside of Schwartz's value theory is that the defined values are very abstract and thus not directly related to behaviour. Several steps are needed to translate abstract values into

Fig. 1. Schwartz's circumplex model of basic values.

more concrete values and ultimately into behavioural choices. How people ground abstract values into concrete choices for action can also differ. Therefore, there is a need to describe this whole system precisely and unambiguously before it can be used for practical purposes. Some work formally describing the relation between abstract values and actions has been developed using value trees in Weide and using them as part of an argumentation process to support decision-making from different perspectives [15]. Similarly, Atkinson and Bench-Capon [2] define the concept of audiences as groups of agents that share a certain value preference which influence their judgement. They use this concept along audience-specific value-based argumentation framework (AVAF), to ground values and explain how arguments can be acceptable for some audiences, as arguments promote values that are preferable for those audiences.

We use the work of Heidari [6] that shows how values can be incorporated in the agent deliberation.

There, a function τ is defined to relate the set of values in Schwartz's model (see Fig. 1) ($Values = V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{10}$) to an importance value (*i.e.*, salience) for each $V_i \in Values$:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau : \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{10}\} &\rightarrow [0, 100] \\ V_i &\mapsto \tau(V_i) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

This importance function is a numerical assessment, ranging from 0 to 100, that quantifies the significance of a value for a given agent (*i.e.*, how often a given value has to be satisfied or how salient it is), such that a higher numerical value indicates greater importance.

Besides this function, [6] defines two more conditions to represent how values are related to each other according to the circumplex defined in Schwartz's theory. For these conditions, they assume "*...each value has the same distance with its neighbours*", representing this by the constant c :

$$\begin{aligned} \textbf{Condition 1: } & \forall i, j \in [1, 10] : 0 \leq |\tau(V_i) - \tau(V_j)| \leq m_{i,j} \\ \text{where } m_{i,j} = & \begin{cases} (|i - j| \cdot c) & \text{if } |i - j| \leq 5 \\ (10 - |i - j| \cdot c) & \text{if } |i - j| > 5 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Condition 1 shows that the range of differences in value importances is narrower the closer the values are to each other on the circumplex model.

$$\textbf{Condition 2: } \begin{cases} \tau(V_i) > 50 & \text{if } \tau(V_j) = 0 \\ 100 - \frac{c}{2} \leq \tau(V_i) + \tau(V_j) \leq 100 + \frac{c}{2} & \text{if } \tau(V_j) \neq 0 \\ & \text{and } \tau(V_i) \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $j = (5 + i) \% 10$

Condition 2 should be understood as follows: if a given value V_i is not present in the model, then $\tau(V_i) = 0$ and its complement is required to have a high importance value (if it is in the model) so that it can have effects on the behaviour of the system [7]. If both values are in the model, their summed importance is bounded above and below. This indicates that values' importance should be complementary to each other to represent conflicting relations between them. Taken together, these conditions constrain the range these value importances can take.

3 Theoretical model

The model presented in this paper contains two main elements: values and context. The values used in our model are based on Schwartz's theory of basic values [13], which is a well-established and accepted theory in the community. Three of these basic values were selected, and for each of these, a more specific value was proposed to align with our scenario (see 4):

- **Universalism:** This value is represented as Environmentalism (E), promoting the reduction of resource consumption (*e.g.*, water).
- **Hedonism:** This value is denoted as Comfort (C), driving agents to have more enjoyable experiences (*e.g.*, having long showers).
- **Benevolence:** Represented as Relatedness (R), this value signifies agents' social relations (*e.g.*, potentially more visitors staying at agents' homes).

Our model defines a context as a specific preorder that establishes a value ordering within the model, accounting for a preference within these values. This preorder, therefore, represents the hierarchy among values, where some are considered more relevant than others in the given context.

Each agent is characterised by the above three values, represented as V_1 , V_4 , and V_{10} ⁶, and a context of their own (referred to as original context) representing the pre-order of these three values that is generated when the agent is initialised. For instance,

$$V_i \succsim V_j \succsim V_k, \text{ for pairwise distinct } i, j, k \in [1, 10] \subseteq \mathbb{N} \quad (4)$$

⁶ Indexes are significant since they are used later to order values according to Schwartz's circumplex representation. We denote Universalism as V_1 , Hedonism as V_4 and Benevolence as V_{10} .

defines a context in our model, which says that V_i is more relevant than V_j , and V_j is more relevant than V_k .

Assuming the concepts described by [6]: value importances as defined by the τ function (Eq. 1) and the conditions to constrain those value importances - **compatibility relation** and **conflicting relation** (Eq. 2 and 3), we relate the **value order** with the τ function,

$$\begin{aligned} V_i \succeq V_j \succeq V_k &\equiv \tau(V_i) \geq \tau(V_j) \geq \tau(V_k), \\ &\text{for pairwise distinct } i, j, k \in [1, 10] \subseteq \mathbb{N} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

effectively moving from a preorder to a partial order and adding an additional condition that constrains value importances ranges. Different contexts (*i.e.*, different value orders) would imply different τ functions, that is, an agent may have to re-map value importances if a different value order is affecting that agent.

For simplicity, we will use the letters E , R , and C to represent the importance given to the values Environmentalism, Relatedness, and Comfort, respectively, instead of $\tau(V_1)$, $\tau(V_4)$, $\tau(V_{10})$. To simplify this representation further, a string containing these letters will be used in the same order as the value order. For instance, $\tau(V_1) \geq \tau(V_{10}) \geq \tau(V_4)$ can be represented as $E \geq R \geq C$ or simply as ERC . The permutation of these three value representations in different positions yields six value orderings: ERC , ECR , REC , RCE , CER , and CRE . The previous conditions (Eq. 2-5) impose constraints on the importance ranges that each value can assume within the model for each possible combination.

Consequently, we can refine an agent's characterisation and define it by its original value order and the importance assigned to each value, which ensures consistency with the prior conditions.

An agent may encounter multiple contexts in parallel, having to determine which one among these to prioritise and employ. Once the conflict is solved and a context is chosen, the agent will shift from its own context to that one. We define the set of possible contexts as \mathcal{C} .

We describe the process of shifting from one context to another as a reordering of agent values:

$$\begin{aligned} V_i \succeq V_j \succeq V_k &\rightarrow V_a \succeq V_b \succeq V_c \\ &\text{for pairwise distinct } i, j, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, 10\} \\ &\text{and } \{a, b, c\} \text{ a permutation of } \{i, j, k\}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Shifting to another context implies rearranging the agent values (*i.e.*, moving its values into a different order), where any V_x could occupy any possible position (*e.g.*, ERC transitioning to CRE). Applying the τ function (Eq. 5) with Eq. 6, we can state that such transition would be

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(V_i) \geq \tau(V_j) \geq \tau(V_k) &\rightarrow \tau'(V_a) \geq \tau'(V_b) \geq \tau'(V_c), \\ &\text{for pairwise distinct } i, j, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, 10\} \\ &\text{and } \{a, b, c\} \text{ a permutation of } \{i, j, k\}. \end{aligned}$$

where τ' is the importance of the values in the new context reflecting the different order of the values; that is, shifting to a new context implies the agent will use a new

τ function to remap value importances in such a way that it complies with the new value order. It is sensible to assume that modifying a value importance may imply some effort (*e.g.*, for a human being that may mean changing a habit, increasing awareness towards your own actions; for a software agent we may want it to put some resistance that represents a similar human behaviour), that is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Effort: } \mathcal{C} \times \text{Importances} \times \mathcal{C} &\rightarrow \mathbb{N} \\ \langle V_i \succeq V_j \succeq V_k \rangle \times (\tau(V_i), \tau(V_j), \tau(V_k)) & \\ \times \langle V_a \succeq V_b \succeq V_c \rangle &\mapsto \mathbb{N} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Although it is possible that in some situations this effort is negligible, we assume in the rest of the paper that this effort is significant enough to be considered. This function uses the agent's importance values, its original context, and the value order of a target context to calculate the effort required to temporarily change value importances to comply with that target context. Once the context is no longer applicable, the agent's value order defaults to its original context and original importances. To quantify this effort, we assume it is linearly proportional to the change in importance. Modifying value importance by ten units requires more effort than just doing it by one unit. We represent this with the following equation:

$$E_i \cdot w_1 + E_j \cdot w_2 + E_k \cdot w_3 \quad (8)$$

In this equation, E_x represents the amount of importance increased or decreased for each V_x to make the new importances consistent with Eq. 4. Such an amount depends on the new positions that each value has adopted in the new context. We assume that the effort of changing a value is proportional to the position the value occupies in the original value order. The variables w_n represent weights that embody this assumption - moving a value from a higher position in the original value order (*e.g.*, V_i) requires more effort than doing so for a value in a lower position (*e.g.*, V_k). That is, modifying the importance of a value that occupies a high position in the value order implies it is a core value compared to the values that come after and, therefore, modifying it is more difficult than doing so for a value that is in a lower position in the value order. Therefore, $w_1 > w_2 > w_3$.

To provide actual values for these weights in our experiments, we used a golden ratio proportion since it is a common ratio in nature. It is possible to use other proportions as long as they comply with the previous equation. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} w_x &= \phi^{N-x}, \text{ where } N \text{ is the amount of} \\ &\text{values being considered and } x \in [1..N] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In our case, $w_1 = 2.671$, $w_2 = 1.618$, $w_3 = 1$

This effort function helps gauge how much effort an agent must invest in changing its context, allowing for a simple way to manage the conflict of selecting a context. Six possible value orders may occur as a target context, determining which values should be modified. Table 1 summarises these different situations. The first column contains the value orders in terms of the agent's values (*i.e.*, V_i, V_j, V_k) whose original context is $V_i \succeq V_j \succeq V_k$, to clearly show the reordering that implies shifting to a different context.

Table 1. Considering the original context as $V_i \geq V_j \geq V_k$, the first column shows the effect of applying one of the six possible parallel contexts as the shift destination. The second column describes the changes to make to modify value importances and comply with the new value order (*i.e.*, τ' has to map new value importances to account for these changes). The last column provides the expression that returns the effort required to shift.

Destination context	Changes	Effort required
$V_i \geq V_j \geq V_k$	None	0
$V_i \geq V_k \geq V_j$	Raise V_k to V_j	$ \tau(V_k) - \tau(V_j) \cdot w_3$
$V_j \geq V_i \geq V_k$	Raise V_j to V_i	$ \tau(V_j) - \tau(V_i) \cdot w_2$
$V_k \geq V_i \geq V_j$	Raise V_k to V_i	$ \tau(V_k) - \tau(V_i) \cdot w_3$
$V_j \geq V_k \geq V_i$	Raise V_j, V_k to V_i	$ \tau(V_j) - \tau(V_i) \cdot w_2 +$ $ \tau(V_k) - \tau(V_i) \cdot w_3$
$V_k \geq V_j \geq V_i$	Raise V_k, V_j to V_i	$ \tau(V_k) - \tau(V_i) \cdot w_3 +$ $ \tau(V_j) - \tau(V_i) \cdot w_2$

In all cases, we assume there are different options for modifying value importances to shift from one value order to another. The second column presents the description of the best option that optimises the effort and the effects on the value importances, given the new value order that rearranged them as such. The last column gives the equation that measures the effort required for that best option. Once the agent has changed context, its importances are temporarily modified accordingly (we refer to them as the actual context/value order the context that the agent shifted to, and the changed importances as actual importances).

4 Scenario

The scenario is set at a time when there is a change from a situation of scarce rain to a drought that affects a territory in a non-uniform way. It consists of an agent-based model of domestic water management with multiple households evenly distributed between two towns (Town₁ and Town₂). Water consumption is measured in terms of showers taken by household members, with shower units serving as the standard measurement. We distinguish between three types of showers (no shower, short shower, and long shower) with associated shower units (0, 1, and 3 units, respectively). Agents decide their daily shower type, consuming more or less water depending on their values and the current context (*i.e.*, value order). During the simulation, Town₁ enacts policies to promote water-saving awareness because of drought during summer. Households may receive visitors that the hosts will try to accommodate. Also, agents may practice sports, which affects the type of shower they will take. The primary objective of this scenario is to illustrate how variations in the context can result in different water consumption patterns. Specifically, it aims to show *how* changes in context can effectively reduce water consumption.

The process starts by determining if there is any parallel context: Firstly, the appearance of visitors in the household and the hosts wanting to accommodate them, introduces a randomly generated context for a whole week, thus making agents in that household deal with a parallel context in their decisions. This context is randomly generated using a discrete uniform distribution across all six possible value orders. The probability of having visitors depends on the household’s agents’ importances for Relatedness (R) and Comfort (C). Since this affects the household collectively, we assume the importance values for R and C used when determining the arrival of visitors, are the highest among the agents living in that household, considering each value individually. Using a sigmoid function (see Eq. 10), we model how households with higher Comfort (relative to Relatedness) prefer having fewer visitors, and higher Relatedness would result in a higher probability of having visitors. The 0.05 factor in the exponential was determined empirically to achieve an appropriate smoothness in the curve.

$$p = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-0.05(R-C)}} \quad (10)$$

Town₁ enacts drought measures in summer that are represented as a parallel context for all agents in that town (*i.e.*, Town₁ enables the value order ERC , to promote water saving measures, hence the Environmentalism value placed in first place and Comfort in last place).

Each individual will compute the effort of moving from its original context to each possible parallel context, if any. The one selected is the parallel context needing the least effort to shift to. We assume an agent tries to move to any available parallel context and not remain in its original context as long as the effort is below a certain effort threshold. This threshold is represented as a parameter of our model. Lower values of this threshold imply the agent will shift only to contexts that require less effort. This parameter allows us to fine-tune experiments where the effort to shift contexts can be low, thus representing cases where the agents may find shifting to contexts is not that cumbersome or the other way around, where the effort to shift is so high that they shift fewer times.

Once the shift to the selected (actual) context is done and value importances are changed, the agent uses these new (actual) importances to select the kind of shower; the agent may decide not to change from its original context since the effort is higher than the mentioned threshold. This selection is performed according to Algorithm 1, treating the choice as a decision tree. The first branch focuses on a water-saving attitude ($\tau'(E) > \tau'(C)$), thus generating more normal or no-shower decisions. The second branch, ($\tau'(C) > \tau'(E)$), on the contrary, generates longer showers. In every case, we use a Bernoulli function to randomly choose whether to shower more or less based on the relative difference in the value importances of *Environmentalism* and *Comfort*.

Lastly, an individual may do sports, thus requiring increasing the length of the shower (from no shower to Short shower and from Short shower to Long shower; if s/he was already taking a long shower, it is not further increased). We represent this with a sports probability equal for all agents.

The arrival of visitors and this sport probability factor add stochastic elements to the scenario. The visitors randomly add a context that agents may shift to, and the sports

Algorithm 1 shouldIShower(E, C)

Input: $E : \tau(\text{Environmentalism}), C : \tau(\text{Comfort})$ **Output:** Shower decision

```

1: if  $E > C$  then
2:   if Bernoulli( $(100 - E)/100$ ) = 1 then
3:     if Bernoulli( $(E - C)/100 + 0.5$ ) = 1 then
4:       long_shower
5:     else
6:       normal_shower
7:     end if
8:   else
9:     no_shower
10:  end if
11: else if  $C > E$  then
12:   if Bernoulli( $C/100$ ) = 1 then
13:     long_shower
14:   else
15:     if Bernoulli( $(C - E)/100 + 0.5$ ) = 1 then
16:       no_shower
17:     else
18:       normal_shower
19:     end if
20:   end if
21: else
22:   normal_shower
23: end if

```

factor adds stochasticity to the length of showers they take. Both account for factors that the scenario may not have explicitly considered and may have a similar effect.

4.1 Experiment Results

The model and scenario presented have been implemented in NetLogo [16] and executed with 240, 960 and 2600 households, containing an average of 2.3 individuals (*i.e.*, around 550, 2200 and 6000 agents). The representation for each value order is evenly distributed among individuals for the whole system. An execution run represents a year in which agents make decisions on a weekly basis. The experiment sweeps through the sports factor, from 0.0 to 0.3, with 0.05 steps. It also sweeps the effort threshold to shift contexts from 0 to 130, with steps of five. We selected this range for the effort threshold so it starts at zero, where almost no shifts are performed, to 130, which allows any shift (*i.e.*, according to the maximum value importance differences using our proposed effort function. It is possible, at zero when all importances are equal, that shifts occur. Each configuration is executed ten times with different random seeds. All these parameters make for 5670 experiment executions. In these experiments, we aim to show that contexts, defined as value orders, have an impact on water consumption and how context shifts produce significant changes in that consumption. Moreover, we

Fig. 2. Boxplots for baseline value importances, by value order. Observe how the distribution of importances depends on the value order. Boxes have been arranged in terms of the relative position of C in contexts. Having C in the middle produces fewer outliers; also, the boxes overlap more. Depending on the value order, the importance ranges are significantly different. This directly affects the effort to shift context, according to our definition of σ .

also aim to show how certain contexts are capable of making more shifts because of the value order itself, resulting in a structural characteristic coming from the representation of Schwartz’s circumplex model and the value order.

Observing Fig. 2, we can see how value importances are distributed along the range [51, 100]. V_i is not restricted and ranges uniformly. However, for V_j and V_k their range depends on which value they represent. In general, depending on the relative position of where C is located in the value order, we can notice how R and E will see their ranges modified. For CER and CRE , C restricts their ranges on the lower part. The value represented by V_k has a small box since, according to Eq. 2, it cannot be more than twenty units further. Something similar happens with ERC and REC , but in this case, since C is at the end, E and R have a wider range. Lastly, when C is in the middle, we find that its range is restricted to the small range defined by V_i and V_k . This will have a significant impact since it implies that value importance differences are smaller and, therefore, the effort to shift will be small as well thus making these contexts to be more prone to change.

For instance, compare CER and RCE in Fig. 3 for $Town_2$. Although the relative positions of E and C remain the same, the position of R determines the value importances of these values. Specifically, if R is in the first or last position, it creates a wider or narrower range for the value importances of C and E . This directly affects the difference between τC and τE and, consequently, the length of the shower. Also in Fig. 3, we can observe how agents adapt their water consumption habits in $Town_1$, which is affected by water restrictions during summer. Not only are agents with a value ordering starting with C the ones consuming more shower units, but they also show a less consequential reaction to the limitation policies encoded as a context with a specific value order (i.e., ERC). A similar low descent in water consumption is observed in

Fig. 3. Data belongs to experiments with effort threshold between 5 and 30, and sport factor between 0.1 and 0.3. Summer season has been highlighted (weeks 26-39) when Town₁ enacts drought measures (*ERC* context). Notice how all contexts exhibit a reduction in shower units in that period. Also, notice the differences between the two groups of value orders: *ERC/ECR/REC* and *CRE/CER/RCE*. The former are water savers, and the latter are water spenders. The differences between those two groups respond to the relative positions of *C* and *E*. Town₂ also exhibits a difference in water consumption due to value order. The difference between *RCE* and *CRE/CER* is relevant. Even though in those cases, *C* is higher than *E*, being *C* in the middle produces shorter showers.

ERC and *ECR* because these two contexts already consume a low amount of shower units. One would argue why *ERC* exhibits a decrease; this is because, before summer, visitors may induce a change of context for those agents that have similar value importances for the three values. In that case, the agent will shift to the visitor’s context. In summer, since Town₁ context is added, those agents will have always a parallel context at effort zero. It is significant the reduction in consumption for *RCE*. Examining Fig. 4 we can see the reason. This figure shows for each week, and for each original value context, the percentage of shifts to contexts that tend to save or spend water (shorter versus longer showers), and shifts to Town₁ context; it also shows the mean shower units. There, *ERC* (as well as *RCE*) exhibits a higher amount of shifts compared to the other value orders. That is due to the relative position of *C*, whose value importance range is enclosed by *E* and *R*. This makes the value importance differences used to compute the effort to shift, to be smaller than other contexts (see Table 1). This is more evident during the summer season, where context *ERC* is always parallel and is massively chosen. On the contrary, for *CER* and *CRE*, Town₁ context is not that popular to shift to since it still requires a significant effort higher than the threshold, explaining the small decrease in shower units.

Results show that context directly impacts agent behaviour towards water consumption (*i.e.*, having shorter or longer showers, if any). Figure 3 shows how agents with a value order that prioritises Environmentalism (E) over Comfort (C) spend significantly fewer shower units across all weeks of the year. Moreover, value importances ranges are constrained by the conditions that represent the circumplex model of values and the value order. These constraints limit the range of value importances so that the relative position of those two values, in the value order, significantly affects the number of shower units. More importantly, our findings suggest that value ordering also affects the capacity to shift from one context to another, which produces changes in that consumption. Given that the effort of shifting depends on the value importance differences, the narrower the value importances ranges are, the easier to shift. Therefore, the effects of Eqs. 2 and 3 along the value order impact water consumption and the capacity to shift whenever a parallel context occurs.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper shows how we can model agents behaving under different contexts. These contexts modify agents' behaviour when deciding what action to perform (*e.g.*, length of the shower). Using Schwartz's circumplex model along with Heidari's equations and τ importance function, we have defined these contexts in terms of preorder of ethical values (namely Universalism (E), Hedonism (C) and Benevolence (R)) thus adding a preference towards those values. Then, we studied the effects of shifting them and changing that value order.

Our proposal allows us to define value orders influencing agents' decisions. Decoupling the actions from the value order distinguishes values and value priorities from the agent's disposition towards the actions it may take in an explicit way. That is, we can define the agent's value order and, independently, using value importance, the disposition when performing the action (*e.g.*, deciding which kind of shower, which depends on the value importance and not the value relative position). This may be considered close to the concept of attitude defined by Schwartz [13, p.16].

Our decision to focus on Universalism and Benevolence as values was driven by the interest in assessing the behaviour of agents with altruistic values to behave in an environmentally friendly way. This was already confirmed through quantitative research by [11] and [10]. By adding the Hedonism value, we introduced a dimension of egoistic goal (*i.e.*, prioritising pleasure or self-gratification) that, despite not being opposite to Universalism or Benevolence, offered room for flexibility as the element leveraging them in our model. However, it would be interesting to study *how* the addition of new values would affect value orderings, in particular those that clearly confront E and C in Schwartz's circumplex model, such as Power or Self-direction. Such addition would significantly constrain value importances and, therefore, agents' behaviour (*i.e.*, opposed values according to Eq. 3 have to balance their importances between them). In our case, context shifts were limited to the conditions of 2 that defined that E 's and R 's importances should be close. Adding new values would open the window to higher variability in value ordering and presumably more complexity in predicting

agents' behaviour, increasing, for instance, the complexity of computing the effort to shift contexts.

Limitations of the model. Our value model assumes homogeneous values since the effort of modifying a value's importance is the same, independent of the value itself. Value importances are constrained by the c factor described in [7]; such a factor assumes the value importances relations between values are also constant and uniform. It is possible, nevertheless, that this parameter c requires calibration to adjust for more realistic situations. In our experiments we assumed this homogeneity since our goal is to explore the effects of value ordering and if changes on it result in realistic, natural changes on agents' behaviour. It is possible that in certain situations the effort to change is negligible (*e.g.*, short periods with a value order changed or insignificant situations). Those cases are accounted for by a high effort threshold. We assumed a simple effort function but think that as long as the value ordering is preserved, the results will be consistent even with a more complex effort function. However, we have not explored how representative those situations are. We have assumed all effort threshold levels uniformly when designing the experiments. Finally, we assumed the agents would always try to shift context whenever there were parallel contexts, and the effort to shift was below the effort threshold. We acknowledge a more realistic process for selecting which context the agent should choose is possible. However, adopting this assumption allowed us to focus on the impact of shifting context and value orders.

This work has served as a first approach to observe how a small group of values have a clear impact on agent's behaviour in a given context. When modelling, there is always the compromise between complexity, realism, and what elements do we want to capture to achieve the model's goals. Adding more values would clearly add much more complexity for computing the effort to shift contexts. In our example, we have used three values, two being close and a third one being not strictly opposed to the other two. One question arises as what if the model have used two confronted values, that is, if value importances ranges have been affected by the second part of Eq. 3. Applying that, it is possible to see that either value importance ranges would have been affected to be either very close or very far away of each other, thus promoting extreme behaviours.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that certain value orders may appear more frequently in societies [14], which is something to consider when using this model regarding the distribution of different value orders.

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Fig. 4. On the left y-axis, the percentage of shifts towards other contexts; we grouped contexts into water savers (*ERC/REC/ECR*) and water spenders *RCE/ECR/CRE*. In darker green, shifts to Town₁ context (*ERC*). On the right y-axis, mean shower units. Data is displayed for all weeks in the simulation. Summer season has been highlighted in yellow (weeks 26-39). Data belongs to experiments with an effort threshold between 5 and 30 and a sports factor between 0.1 and 0.3. Each subplot focuses on Town₁ agents with a specific original context (in the title). Notice the shower unit reduction that takes place in summer. For the *ERC* subplot, the Town₁ context is not reflected since it is always chosen and is not considered a shift. In all cases, the changing context has produced a clear effect; observe how the context with *C* in the mid position of the value order have a higher amount of shifts, indicating that these value orders need less effort to shift.